

THE EVALUATION OF DIFFERENT AGRO WASTES FOR CULTIVATION OF MILKY MUSHROOM

B. S. Vasmatkar, S.L. Badgujar P. M. Khandare,

Department of Plant Pathology,
College of Agriculture, VNMKV Parbhani, MH, India.padma.khandare@rediffmail.com

(MS Received: 15.02.2024; MS Revised:20.03.2024; MS Accepted:21.03.2024)

MS 3203

(RESEARCH PAPER IN PLANT PATHOLOGY)

Abstract

Present study entitled, "Cultivation of Milky Mushroom (*Calocybe indica*) in Marathwada region" was carried out in Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, V.N.M.K.V., Parbhani. The present study attempts were made To know the effect of different straw substrates on growth and yield of *C. indica*. Among the eight different straw substrates, Wheat straw was superior, which was recorded minimum days for spawn run, pinhead initiation with highest number of pinheads and matured fruiting bodies. Also recorded maximum length of stipe and diameter of stipe and diameter of pileus with maximum weight of sporophore, maximum yield and biological efficiency (B.E.) of *C. indica* in wheat straw substrate.

Keywords: *Calocybe*, Wheat, Sporohore, Biological, Cultivation, Straw.

Introduction

Mushrooms are liked for their delicious flavour, low calorific value and high protein contents, vitamins of B group and minerals. It contains 20-40% proteins on a dry weight basis and no cholesterol and is almost fat free (Walde *et al.*, 2006). Mushrooms are good source of non-starchy carbohydrates, dietary fiber, protein, mineral and vitamins (Kulshreshtha *et al.*, 2009). Nutritionally it can be placed between meat and vegetables and therefore mushrooms are called as vegetable meat or slimming food. It is tropical edible fungus known for its robust, fleshy milky white sporocarps, long shelf life and taste, which was first collected in wild form from West Bengal (India) by Purkayastha and Chandra in 1974. It is also known as "Dudh Chhatta" because of its milky white appearance and large sized sporophores or as "white summer mushroom" because of its tropical nature. Its robust size, sustainable yield, attractive color, delicacy, long shelf-life and lucrative market value have attracted the attention of both mushroom consumers and prospective growers. This species is suitable for hot humid climate and can be cultivated in high temperature and high humidity areas. This mushroom requires a temperature of 30-35°C and relative humidity of 70-80% for cultivation which is conducive to environmental conditions of west part of India (Amin *et al.*, 2010, Gitte *et al.*, 2014). Milky mushroom with its ability to grow fairly at high temperatures seems to be the best alternative to such mushrooms. The mushroom is well appreciated due to its large sized milky white sporophores, simple production technology and low capital investment.

Materials And Methods

An experiment was conducted at Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani. An experiment was conducted during 2019-2020 in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) under room conditions. There were eight treatments each with three replications. These were Soybean straw, paddy straw, wheat straw, gram straw, pigeon pea straw, sawdust, sorghum leaves and sugarcane leaves.

Pure culture

Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), the common laboratory culture medium was used as basal medium for isolation, purification, multiplication and maintenance of the pure culture of *Calocybe indica*.

Master and commercial spawn:

Wheat grains were used for the preparation of master and commercial spawn of *C. indica* using polypropylene bags (8 x 12").

Source of material:

The spawn of *C. indica* were obtained from Mushroom Research Station, Solan (H.P.) and pure culture of the *C. indica* was made from commercial spawn. The pure culture was sub cultured on Potato Dextrose Agar medium and stored at 4°C until used for the entire work.

General Methods**Isolation, Purification and maintenance**

Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium was prepared for isolation, purification and maintenance of culture of *C. indica* with the help of the following constituents:

Potato peeled and sliced: 200 gm

Dextrose: 20 gm

Agar-agar: 20 gm

Distilled water: 1000 ml

20 ml of each medium was poured in sterilized petriplates. A little amount of streptomycin was added in PDA at the time of pouring to prevent bacterial contamination. After solidifications of medium the plates were centrally inoculated with 5 mm disc of actively growing mushroom of *C. indica*. The petriplates were incubated at 30°C for 2 to 5 days. The pure culture was maintained on PDA slants and kept in refrigerator at 4°C for further studies.

Preparation of spawn:

For preparation of master spawn healthy wheat grains were cleaned and washed with water 3 times to remove the dust particles and weed seed and these grains were soaked 6-8 hrs. in clean water. After soaking, water was changed and then these seeds were boiled. After 10 minute of boiling the container was removed from the burner and then covered with lid and kept for 5-10 minutes. Then excess water was drained out and grains were spread on blotting sheet and were allowed to surface dry for 2 hours. These grains were then mixed with (2.5 %) calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) on (w/w) basis for adjusting the pH of grains at 6.5 - 7.5 as well as for checking the coagulation and clumping of the grains. About 250-300 gm mixture was filled in each 500 ml conical flasks which were plugged tight and sterilized at 20 lbs psi pressure (126.5°C) for 2 hours. After cooling at room temperature flasks were transferred in laminar air flow cabinet and were given UV light exposure for 15-20 minutes to remove the surface contaminants. After cooling, inoculation was done with active growing mycelium of *C. indica*, and then incubated at 30°C in BOD incubator for 20-25 days till adequate growth was obtained. The fully grown spawn bottles were kept at 25°C. The spawn thus prepared was used for preparation of commercial spawn.

Mushroom bed preparation :

The dry straw substrates were chopped into small pieces (3-5cm long). The chopped substrates were weighed and then soaked in cold water mixed with 75 ppm carbendazim and 500 ppm formaldehyde for 14-16 hours as per the method described by Vijay and Sohi (1987). After soaking substrates were taken out and excess water were drained off. After draining excess water, these straws were weighed. These straws were then sterilized in autoclave at 20 Lbs psi for 20 minutes. After autoclaving the straws were cooled down to ambient temperature and used for filling the polythene bags. The straw was spread over on slopy, cemented floor till the moisture content of straw remained 65-70 per

cent. Before spawning, formaldehyde was sprinkled on floor and substrates were inoculated with spawn. The mouth of spawned bag was tied with the help of cotton tag and for perforation, 8-10 holes were made in each bag with the help of sterilized needle to allow free passage of air within the bags. The spawned bags were kept in mushroom growing room, where appropriate temperature (25-35°C) and relative humidity (80-90 %) were maintained by frequently sprinkling of water on walls and floor. After complete colonization of substrate by mushroom mycelium (spawn run), casing was done.

Casing of the bed

After completion of spawn run, the mouth of bags was opened and 3cm thick layer of casing materials was placed on the surface of spawned substrate.

Watering

The cased bags were kept for fructification in the cropping house. Watering was done twice or thrice everyday on the top of casing soil to maintain wetness.

Picking of the mushroom

Mature sporophores were picked up just before the edges of the pileus begin to dry or showed yellowness. Picking was done by slight twisting and pulling of sporophores. Three flushes were harvested from the same bed at an interval of 10-15 days.

Observations recorded:

Days required for spawn run

Days required for pinhead initiation

Number of pinheads per / bed

Table 1. Studies on spawn run rate and pinhead initiation of *C.indica* on different agro wastes as straw

Tr. No.	Treatments	Average days required *for					Pinhead initiation after casing	Average no. of*	
		Percent mycelia coverage on Beds (spawn run)						pinheads	MFB
		10%	25%	50%	75%	100%			
T1	Soybean straw	5.67	9.67	13.67	17.67	20.67	12.67	53.33	8.67
T2	Paddy straw	5.33	9.33	13.33	17.33	20.33	11.00	58.33	9.67
T3	Wheat straw	5.00	9.00	12.67	16.67	19.67	10.67	60.00	11.33
T4	Gram straw	7.00	11.67	15.67	19.67	22.67	14.33	50.67	7.33
T5	Pigeon pea straw	7.67	14.33	17.67	21.00	24.00	15.00	42.00	6.67
T6	Sawdust	9.00	13.67	19.00	23.67	27.67	16.67	33.00	5.33
T7	Sorghum leaves	6.67	10.67	15.00	19.00	22.00	13.33	49.33	7.33
T8	Sugarcane leaves	6.67	11.00	15.33	19.67	22.33	14.00	49.67	7.00
S.E.m. ±		0.48	0.67	0.64	0.67	0.70	0.63	3.53	0.47
C.D. (P=0.01)		2.00	2.79	2.66	2.79	2.92	2.62	14.57	1.94

(*: Average of three replications)

Number of pinheads

Maximum 60 pinheads were observed in T3 (wheat straw) which were at par with) with 58 and 53.33 pinheads in treatment T2 (paddy straw) and T1 (soybean straw respectively. Minimum pinheads 25.00 were observed in treatment T6 (sawdust).

Number of matured fruiting bodies

Maximum matured fruiting bodies 11.33 were observed in T3 (wheat straw), which were at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw) with 9.67 MFB and T1 (soybean straw) with 8.67 MFB. Average 5.33 less matured fruiting bodies were in treatment T6 (sawdust). Lowest mortality was observed in T3 (wheat straw) with 81.11 per cent which was at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw), T1 (soybean straw) and was 83.43 83.75 per cent, respectively. Highest mortality were percentage 85.91 was observed in T8 (sugarcane leaves) followed by T7 (sorghum leaves) 85.14.

Weight of sporophore

Maximum weight of sporophore was observed in T3 (wheat straw), 96.80 gm, which was at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw) with 95.00

Number of matured fruiting bodies / bed

Length of stipe (cm)

Diameter of stipe (cm)

Diameter of pileus (cm)

Weight of sporophore (g)

Average yield of mushroom (g)

Average dry weight (g)

Biological efficiency (%)

Fresh wt. of harvested mushroom

BE (%) = ----- x 100

Dry wt. of substrate

Result And Discussion

Different eight agro wastes like Soybean straw, paddy straw, wheat straw, gram straw, pigeon pea straw, sawdust, sorghum leaves and sugarcane leaves which were easily available in the region were evaluated to study the yield performance of *C.indica*.

Spawn run

Minimum days required for spawn run in T₃ (wheat straw) were 19.67 days which were at par with treatment T₂ (paddy straw) with 20.33 days and T₁ (soybean straw) 20.67 days. Maximum days required for spawn run in treatment T₆ (sawdust) were 27.67 days.

Days for pinhead formation

Minimum time required for pinhead formation in T₃ (wheat straw) which was 10.67 days and it was at par with treatment T₂ (paddy straw), 11.00 days and T₁ (soybean straw), 12.67 days. Maximum time required for spawn run was 16.67 days in treatment T₆ (sawdust).

gm and T1 (soybean straw) with 93.70. 80.59 gm weight of sporophore was observed in treatment T6 (sawdust) which was minimum.

Yield

Maximum yield was observed in T3 (wheat straw), 1099.87 gm, which was at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw) with 921.93 gm and T1 (soybean straw) with 815.66 gm. Lowest yield was observed in treatment T6 (sawdust), 431.53 gm.

Dry weight

Maximum dry weight observed in T3 (wheat straw) was 135.92 gm, which was at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw) with 88.11 gm and T1 (soybean straw) with 77.85. Least dry weight 38.95 gm was observed in treatment T6 (sawdust).

Biological efficiency

Maximum biological efficiency observed in T3 (wheat straw) was 109.98%, which was at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw) with 92.19% and T1 (soybean straw) with 81.56%. Minimum biological efficiency 43.15 percent was observed in treatment T6 (sawdust).

Table 2. Yield performance of *C.indica* on different straws (Average of 3 picking)

Tr. No.	Treatments	Av. Number *of		Average			Av. Size** of		
		Mortality %	Wt. of Sporophore (gm)	Yield (gm)	Dry weight(g m)	B.E.(%)	Stipe length (cm)	Stipe Dia. (cm)	Pileus Dia. (cm)
T1	Soybean straw	83.75	93.70	815.66	77.85	81.56	12.53	4.57	10.53
T2	Paddy straw	83.43	95.00	921.93	88.11	92.19	13.20	4.60	11.10
T3	Wheat straw	81.11	96.80	1099.87	135.92	109.98	14.40	5.00	12.47
T4	Gram straw	85.53	92.95	684.05	64.84	68.40	11.53	4.10	9.63
T5	Pigeon pea straw	84.13	82.11	549.80	41.09	54.98	9.87	3.67	7.83
T6	Sawdust	3.84	80.59	431.53	80.59	431.53	6.73	2.47	5.33
T7	Sorghum leaves	85.14	85.71	630.07	85.71	630.07	9.93	3.73	7.97
T8	Sugarcane leaves	85.91	90.00	631.37	90.00	631.37	10.20	4.03	7.97
S.E.m. ±		3.53		0.10	57.76		0.39	0.12	0.34
C.D. (P=0.01)		14.57		0.45	238.60		1.62	0.49	1.42

(*: Average of three replication, **: Average of five sporophore)

Length of stipe

Maximum length of stipe observed in T3 (wheat straw) was 14.40 cm, which was at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw) with 13.20 cm and T1 (soybean straw) with 12.50. Minimum length of stipe was observed in treatment T6 (sawdust) i.e 6.73 cm.

Diameter of stipe

Maximum diameter of stipe observed in T3 (wheat straw) was 5.00 cm, which was at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw) with 4.60 cm and T1 (soybean straw) with 4.57 cm. Minimum diameter of stipe was observed in treatment T6 (sawdust) i.e 2.47 cm.

Diameter of pileus

Table 3. The economics of the production of fresh mushroom per bed of *C. indica* using different straw substrate

Tr. No.	Treatments	Total inputs (Rs)	Yield/bed* (gm)	Gross income (Rs.)	Net benefit (Rs.)	Net benefit cost ratio (Rs)
T1	Soybean straw	34.5	815.66	81.57	47.07	1.36
T2	Paddy straw	38	921.93	92.19	54.19	1.43
T3	Wheat straw	37	1099.87	109.99	72.99	1.97
T4	Gram straw	35	684.05	68.41	33.41	0.95
T5	Pigeon pea straw	35	549.8	54.98	19.98	0.57
T6	Sawdust	34	431.53	43.15	9.15	0.27
T7	Sorghum leaves	34	630.07	63.01	29.01	0.85
T8	Sugarcane leaves	34	631.37	63.14	29.14	0.86

(*: Average of three replications)

In the studies (Table 3) that Wheat straw yielded net benefit-cost ratio of 1.97 followed by Paddy straw with 1.43 and Soybean straw with 1.36. Less net cost - benefit ratio 0.27 was obtained in Sawdust.

In these investigations, the early spawn run (19.67 days) and pinhead initiation after casing (10.67 days) was observed in wheat straw. This is in agreement with the earlier reports of several workers. Gitte, (2014) observed minimum days for spawn run (15.67 days) and pinhead initiation (28.67 days) in wheat straw followed by paddy straw (17.67 days) for spawn run and (32.33 days) for pinhead initiation of milky mushroom. Similar observations were also recorded by Bhatt *et al.*, (2007), Chaubey *et al.*, (2010), Singh (2017), Singh *et al.*, (2017), Suman *et al.*, (2018) who reported wheat straw as the best substrate for early spawn run and pinhead initiation of *C. indica*. It was found that maximum number of pinheads (60) and no. of matured fruiting bodies (11.33) observed in wheat straw substrate followed by paddy straw. Similarly, Maximum no. of fruiting bodies (24.33) in wheat straw followed by paddy straw (23.33) observed by Gitte, (2014). Maximum weight of sporophore (96.80 gm) yield (1099.87 gm) and Biological efficiency (109.98%) observed in wheat straw, the result very close to Suman *et al.*, (2018) who observed maximum weight of sporophore (130.6 gm) and yield (1283.6 gm) in wheat straw, while Gitte, (2014)

Maximum diameter of pileus observed in T3 (wheat straw) was 12.47 cm, which was at par with treatment T2 (paddy straw) with 11.10 cm and T1 (soybean straw) with 10.53 cm. Minimum diameter 5.33 cm of pileus was observed in treatment T6 (sawdust).

Economics of mushroom

(Soybean straw @ 2.5/kg, Paddy straw @ Rs. 6/kg; Wheat straw @ Rs. 5/kg, Gram straw @ Rs. 3/kg, Pigeon pea straw @ Rs.3/kg, Sawdust @ Rs.2/kg, Sorghum leaves @ Rs.2 /kg, Sugarcane leaves @ Rs. 2/kg, Casing material @ Rs. 8/kg, Spawn @ Rs. 14/bag (wheat grain based spawn); Polythene bag @ Rs. 5/bag; Miscellaneous charges @ Rs. 5/bag; Mushroom selling price @ Rs. 100/kg fresh mushroom).

observed maximum yield (1463 gm and biological efficiency (BE) (146.3%) in wheat straw followed by paddy straw (1324 gm). Maximum length of stipe (14.40cm), diameter of stipe (5.00 cm) and diameter of pileus (12.47 cm) observed in wheat straw substrate. Similarly, maximum length of stipe (7.86 cm) and diameter of pileus (7.66 cm) observed in wheat straw by Gitte, (2014) for cultivation of milky mushroom. Similarly, Singh (2017), Singh *et al.*, (2017), Suman *et al.*, (2018) also reported wheat straw as the best substrate for cultivation of *C. indica*.

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PLATE - I

Matured fruiting bodies of *C. indica* on different straw substrates

PLATE - II

Matured fruiting bodies of *C. indica* on different straw substrates